

Deliverable report for

Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement Number 101069888

Deliverable D6.3

“Reports to the European Commission”

Due date of deliverable: 2023/12/31

Actual submission date: 2024/01/29

Identifier:	D6.3: H ₂ ICE installed and adapted to UPV's test bench
Beneficiaries:	CONSORTIUM
Work package/task:	WP6 / Task 6.3
Document status:	draft / <u>final</u>
Confidentiality:	confidential / restricted / <u>public</u>

This project is funded under Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement no 101069888

Lead beneficiary for this deliverable: CONSORTIUM (or) PARTNER NAME

Dissemination Level:			
PU	Defined in the DoW	Public	Yes /No
PP		Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	Yes/ No
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CO		Confidential, only for partners of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	Yes/ No

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1. Abbreviations

CO: Confidential

D: Deliverable

DEM: Demonstrator

DoA: Description of the Action

DoW: Description of Work

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

GA: Grant Agreement

IPR Intellectual Property Rights

M: Month

PC: Project Coordinator

PM: Project Manager

PO: Project Officer

PP: Program Participants

PU: Public

RE: Restricted

SC: Steering Committee

SM: Sales Manager

SME: Small and Medium Enterprises

SQS: Seminal Quality System

T: Task

TM: Technical Manager

WP: Work Package

H2: Hydrogen

DI: Direct Injection

PFI: Port Fuel Injection

DOHC: Double Overhead Camshaft

RPEMS: Rapid Prototype Engine Management System

EGR: Exhaust Gas Recirculation

UPV: Universitat Politècnica de València (Polytechnic University of Valencia)

2. Summary

This report refers to the previous two deliverables D6.1 and D6.2. It outlines the engine set-up on the test bed including instrumentation and a short description of the test bed and measurement devices.

3. Complete Engine Set-Up on Test bed

3.1 Sensors

The engine is equipped with the usual temperature and pressure sensors for the intake, exhaust, high-pressure EGR system, oil, and coolant circuit. The instrumentation layout (i.e., position and naming of each sensor) was already outlined in Deliverable D6.1. Photos of the sensor positions were also already included in the Deliverable D6.1 report.

The originally designated low-pressure indication sensor AVL – GS11D-S0 was changed to the Kistler – 4045A5. The high-pressure indication sensor is still the AVL – GH15DK with a high knock protection.

A lambda sensor is installed in the exhaust pipe for the control of the fuel amount with the AVL RPEMS. Additionally, as a backup and for plausibility checks, the lambda will be also calculated from the measured engine inlet mass flows (H_2 and air) and from the exhaust measurement device.

3.2 Measurement devices

A Horiba measurement device for the exhaust components measures the NO_x , THC, CO_2 and O_2 emissions.

An extra device for the H_2 measurement in the exhaust pipe will be installed in 2024. The blow-by is measured by an AVL Blow-by meter.

An *AVL Indicom* Indication system delivers all the in-cylinder related measurements and calculations out of the high-resolution cylinder pressure signal: 10%, 25%, 50%, and 90% mass burned values, start of injection, duration of injection, and ignition time.

For measuring the H_2 mass flow going into the engine a digital thermal mass flow controller from Bronkhorst with the specification F-203AV-1M0-AGD-55-V is used.

The air mass flow meter Elster Instromet RVG G100 DN80 PN16 is used for measuring the intake air mass flow of the engine.

A H_2 measurement device for the H_2 slip measurement in the exhaust gas, is planned to be rented and/or bought from UPV from early 2024 onwards.

3.3 Engine run

The engine was already fired and the in-cylinder pressure of a low load operating point is shown in the diagram below.

Figure 1: In-cylinder pressure signal in one operating point

AVL PUMA is installed on the test bed and is used to control the dyno and the measurement devices. Furthermore the signals from the indication system and from the Application Software for the RPEMS are also hooked up to PUMA. By this, all the measurement channels of the main engine parameters, like engine speed, torque, mass flows, temperatures, and pressures of all gases and liquids that are necessary for the engine operation, are centrally stored in the PUMA system.

3.4 Engine installation on test cell

The pictures below show how the engine is installed on the test bed including the connected test bed measurement devices and media conditioning devices.

Figure 2: Engine installed on test bed

Figure 3: Front view with AVL RPEMS

Figure 4 Engine back view including the dynamometer

Figure 5 – Intake side of the engine with common-rails for DI and PFI injectors

Figure 6 – EGR into the intake pipe

Figure 7 – EGR taking of the exhaust pipe

Figure 8 – Horiba emission measurement bench

Figure 9 – Test bed at UPV